

Evaluation of the Factors Impacting the Performance of Nurses Working in Duhok Governmental Hospitals in the Kurdistan Region, Iraq

Bangeen Sisin Ahmed ✉

Department of Public Health, College of Health and Medical Technology, Shekhan, Duhok Polytechnic University, Duhok, Iraq

Ismael Shukri Murad

Department of Public Health, College of Health and Medical Technology, Shekhan, Duhok Polytechnic University, Duhok, Iraq

Mohammed Haydar Mosa

Department of Public Health, College of Health and Medical Technology, Shekhan, Duhok Polytechnic University, Duhok, Iraq

Abstract

Hospitals play a crucial role in community health moving forward and the significance of nurses, as an essential component in healthcare services is underlined. It emphasizes that nurses are interested in patient care not only brain, emotional social and spiritual needs. Furthermore, it considers issues that drive performance of the nurses regarding salary structure and working conditions. The study aims to evaluate the factors affecting nurses' performance in government hospitals in Duhok city, Iraq. Data was collected from 110 nurses using a questionnaire that was assessed by specialists. Findings show a wide range of concerns, from poor public perception of the nursing role to confusion over what we actually do and even being treated poorly by colleagues or patients. Inadequate financial income, risk of infection and stress were other issues that exacerbated the profession. The results also indicate problems related to how the leave of absence is granted and lack of clear task norms that compromise nurses' performance. This study concluded that there was a low level of salary among nurses and a low level of career development.

Introduction

One type of healthcare facility and location where efforts are made to promote community health is the hospital. Knowing this, the hospital has a responsibility to focus on providing health services to patients who depend on human resources as a health service facility [1]. One element of hospital services are nurses, who serve as a standard by which to measure the caliber of medical care provided at the facility. Nurses now see patients' psychosocial requirements in addition to their physical ones, and they consider their patients' needs to be social, psychological, spiritual, and physiological [2].

The job of nurses is also influenced by a wide range of circumstances. The most crucial factors include pay structure, type of work, prospects for growth, work group, physical conditions of the job, effective service education program, peer relationships, and decision-

making involvement. The degree of working circumstances can be improved or decreased by changing these parameters [3]. Numerous studies have shown that one of the key elements in determining the quality of health services is the performance of nurses. Outstanding benefits for nurses by advancing the best standards of nursing care and enhancing patient outcomes [4]. Categorize the many variables influencing nurses' performance as employees into three categories based on their viewpoints: situational, regulatory, and individual variations [5].

The study intends to assess the variables influencing nurses' work performance and to determine the correlation between a few sociodemographic variables (nurse age, gender, marital status, educational attainment, and years of tenure) and the variables influencing nurses' work performance at all of Duhok City's governmental hospitals.

More Information

How to cite this article: Ahmed BS, Murad IS, Mosa MH. Evaluation of the Factors Impacting the Performance of Nurses Working in Duhok Governmental Hospitals in the Kurdistan Region, Iraq. *Eur J Med Health Res*, 2026;4(1):272-7.

DOI: 10.59324/ejmhr.2026.4(1).38

Keywords:

Evaluates,
Factors,
Performance,
Risk,
Infection,
Healthcare.

Received	05.01.2026
Revised	26.01.2026
Accepted	29.01.2026
Published	xx.02.2026

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. The license permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, on the condition that users give exact credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons license, and indicate if they made any changes.

Methodology

Setting of the Study

The study was conducted in all five Ministry of Health hospitals in Duhok city, Kurdistan Rion of Iraq.

Design of the Study

A cross-sectional design used to achieve the aim of the study. The data for the original study was collected from nurses in Ministry of Health hospitals in Duhok city, and started from the 10th of July 2024 to the 1st of August 2024.

Sample of the Study

Sample for this study selected (110) nurses from (428) of the total nurses taken according to statistic of hospitals during year 2024. The systematic random sampling technique included nurses who are working in Ministry of Health hospitals in Duhok city and available at the time of data collection, and nurses acceptable to a participation in the study.

The Study Instrument

The researcher prepared a questionnaire as part of the study tool, and it was evaluated by many referees and based on a literature review to verify that it was adequate in terms of both culture and language. The study's instruments were divided into two sections following the organization of the data gathered from referees:

The first section of the survey asked questions about years of job experience, age, gender, and educational attainment. The questionnaire's second part included five dimensions that have an impact on nurses' work that are low patient awareness and education, difficulties in the nursing profession and the heavy workload, insufficient moral and financial incentives, rigidity in the workplace and ineffective leadership, and inadequate task description and standards are all contributing factors. Every item has a 3-point rating scale labeled "Never/ /Sometimes/ always" that ranges

from 0 to 2. The questionnaire was given to ten nurses between June 2, 2024, and June 17, 2024, in order to assess its reliability. Fifteen days later, the same group received another administration of the questionnaire to determine the association between the pre- and post-test scores. We made advantage of Pearson's Coefficient Correlation.

Ethical Consideration

Prior to their inclusion in the trial, nurses were provided with a clear elucidation of the study's objective. A well-informed verbal permission was acquired. Every participant was questioned separately using the study instruments stated above. The individuals were given a guarantee that all the gathered data would solely be utilized for research purposes. The anonymity, secrecy, privacy, safety, and protection of the participants were ensured. Moreover, the local ethical approval was obtained from the Ethical Committee of Directorate General of Health Directorate of Planning Scientific Research Division to conduct the study.

Statistical Analysis

The sample description was calculated using percentages and frequency. When $P < 0.05$, the Chi-square test was conducted to determine the link between the level of sufficiency & the variables.

Results

The socio-demographic traits are shown in Table 1. The age groups that made up the largest percentage, (27 to 37) years old, accounted for (57.3 %) of the total. that (50.9%) female made up the majority of nurses. The percentage of graduates with a nursing diploma was greater (54.5%) than the percentage of graduates with a nursing college degree (18.2%). Of those with service years ranging from two to twelve years, (65.5%) had completed their education, and (10%) had service years exceeding (23) years.

Table 1: The Study Sample's Distribution Frequency and Percentage for Sociodemographic Characteristics (n = 110)

Socio-demographic characteristics	F.	%	
Age Mean= 38.7 S.D =7.2	27-37 years	63	57.3
	38-48 years	37	33.6
	49-56	10	9.1
	Total	110	100%
Gender	Male	54	49.1
	Female	56	50.9
	Total	110	100%
Level of education	Less than diploma	30	27.3
	Diploma	60	54.5
	College and above	20	18.2
	Total	110	100%
Services years	2-12 years	72	65.5
	13-23 years	27	24.5
	Above 23 years	11	10
	Total	110	100%

Table 2 shows the mainly were the negative view of workers in the nursing profession and their treatment as servants were (72.7 %), then the inability of patients to comprehend the role of nurses were (52.7 %), patient mistrust of nursing professionals was (43.6 %),

lack of respect from coworkers or patients for the nurse was (36.4 %) and the factor the focus of work is on interpersonal relationships, not competence was (31.8 %).

Table 2: Answers from Nurses Regarding Patients' Levels of Awareness and Education Factors on Three Levels of the Scale, Broken Down by Total Frequencies and Percentages

L.	Low degree of awareness and education among patient	Never		Sometime		Always	
		F	%	F	%	F	%
1	The inability of patients to comprehend the role of nurses	30	27.3	22	20	58	52.7
2	Lack of respect from coworkers or patients for the nurse	10	9.09	60	54.5	40	36.4
3	The negative view of workers in the nursing profession and their treatment as servants	3	2.73	27	24.5	80	72.7
4	The focus of work is on interpersonal relationships, not competence	33	30	42	38.2	35	31.8
5	Patient mistrust of nursing professionals	24	21.8	38	34.5	48	43.6

Table 3 shows the mainly were the risk of infection among nurses while they are at work were (95.5%), then the level of difficulty in the field in relation to other professions were (91.8%), nursing professionals are exposed to psychological pressure due to their

dealings with patients was (89.1 %), the existence of a night shift system in the nursing profession was (54.5 %) and the factor nursing professionals were assaulted (verbally and physically) by some patients and their relatives was (9.09 %).

Table 3: Answers from Nurses Regarding Challenges of the Nursing Field and the Intense Workload Factors on Three Levels of the Scale, Broken Down by Total Frequencies and Percentages

L.	Challenges of the nursing field and the intense workload	Never		Sometime		Always	
		F	%	F	%	F	%
1	The level of difficulty in the field in relation to other professions	1	0.91	8	7.27	101	91.8
2	The risk of infection among nurses while they are at work	1	0.91	4	3.64	105	95.5
3	The existence of a night shift system in the nursing profession	10	9.09	40	36.4	60	54.5
4	Nursing professionals are exposed to psychological pressure due to their dealings with patients	2	1.82	10	9.09	98	89.1
5	Nursing professionals were assaulted (verbally and physically) by some patients and their relatives	30	27.3	70	63.6	10	9.09

Table 4 shows the mainly were Lack of financial income for the nursing profession were (99.1%), then lack of opportunity to continue university education and postgraduate studies for nursing practitioners were (90.9 %), low salaries compared to the responsibilities

and requirements of nursing service was (81.8 %), low opportunities for career advancement in the profession was (45.5 %) and the factor Lack of opportunities for continuing education and training courses in the field of work was (4.55%).

Table 4: Answers from Nurses Regarding Inadequate Moral and Financial Incentives Factors on Three Levels of the Scale, Broken Down by Total Frequencies and Percentages

L.	Inadequate moral and financial incentives	Never		Sometime		Always	
		F	%	F	%	F	%
1	Lack of financial income for the nursing profession	0	0	1	0.91	109	99.1
2	Low opportunities for career advancement in the profession	10	9.09	50	45.5	50	45.5
3	Low salaries compared to the responsibilities and requirements of nursing service	9	8.18	11	10	90	81.8
4	Lack of opportunities for continuing education and training courses in the field of work	95	86.4	10	9.09	5	4.55
5	Lack of opportunity to continue university education and postgraduate studies for nursing practitioners.	5	4.55	5	4.55	100	90.9

Figure 1 indicates that there are real problems that hinder nurses’ performance from the nurses’ point of view. Whereas inadequate moral and financial incentives come first, while lack of flexibility at work and weak leadership come last.

Table 5 shows the high percentage about having trouble getting time off because there aren't enough nurses was (87.3%), Lack of flexibility in annual leave dates was (68.2 %), having to work more than the required hours were (27.3%) Some officials in the supervising administration dominate nursing practitioners. (13.6 %) Insufficient flexibility in work shifts (7.27 %).

Figure 1: Rank Factors Impacting the Performance of Nurses from Nurse’s Point of View

Table 5: Answers from Nurses Regarding Lack of Flexibility at Work and Weak Leadership Factors on Three Levels of the Scale, Broken Down by Total Frequencies and Percentages

L.	Lack of flexibility at work and weak leadership	Never		Sometime		Always	
		F	%	F	%	F	%
1	Insufficient flexibility in work shifts	17	15.5	85	77.3	8	7.27
2	Lack of flexibility in annual leave dates.	5	4.55	30	27.3	75	68.2
3	Having to work more than the required hours.	10	9.09	70	63.6	30	27.3
4	Some officials in the supervising administration dominate nursing practitioners.	17	15.5	78	70.9	15	13.6
5	Having trouble getting time off because there aren't enough nurses	3	2.73	11	10	96	87.3

Table 6 indicates the factors Inadequate task definition and lack of standards which was the obligations imposed on nurses are incompatible with the authority and powers at their disposal. (89.1 %), lack of clarity of the tasks and role assigned to the nursing practitioner

(80%), inability to discern between different professional levels because of workers' uniforms (27.3%), Lack of fairness standards in promotions (14.5 %), and being required to carry out duties outside the scope of the nursing profession (6.36%).

Table 6: Answers from Nurses Regarding Inadequate Task Definition and Lack of Standards Factors on Three Levels of the Scale, Broken Down by Total Frequencies and Percentages

L.	Inadequate task definition and lack of standards	Never		Sometime		Always	
		F	%	F	%	F	%
1	Lack of clarity of the tasks and role assigned to the nursing practitioner.	8	7.27	14	12.7	88	80
2	The obligations imposed on nurses are incompatible with the authority and powers at their disposal.	2	1.82	10	9.09	98	89.1
3	Being required to carry out duties outside the scope of the nursing profession	87	79.1	16	14.5	7	6.36
4	Lack of fairness standards in promotions.	7	6.36	87	79.1	16	14.5
5	Inability to discern between different professional levels because of workers' uniforms	12	10.9	68	61.8	30	27.3

Table 7 shows that there are no significant statistical factors affecting nursing staff performance and their age, gender, services years, and there is a significant

relationship between the workforce staffing factors and their level of education.

Table 7: Examining the Disparities Between the Five Nurse Factors and Their Sociodemographic Features

Socio Demographic Characteristics	Test	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5
Age	F.	2.85	0.97	1.40	2.22	1.68
	P.	0.06	0.38	0.25	0.07	0.19
	Sig.	N. S	N. S	N. S	N. S	N. S
Gender	T.	1.56	1.62	-1.33	1.11	-0.26
	P.	0.12	0.11	0.19	0.27	0.79
	Sig.	N. S	N. S	N. S	N. S	N. S
Level of education	F.	4.16	6.20	6.15	4.06	4.38
	P.	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.03
	Sig.	Sig.	Sig	Sig.	Sig.	Sig.
Services years	F.	1.23	0.93	2.63	1.1	2.67
	P.	0.30	0.40	0.78	0.3	0.4
	Sig.	N. S	N. S	N. S	N. S	N.S.

Note: F1: Low degree of awareness and education among patient Factors, F2: Challenges of the nursing field and the intense workload Factors, F3: Inadequate moral and financial incentives Factors, F4: Lack of flexibility at work and weak leadership Factors, F5: Inadequate task definition and lack of standards Factors

Discussion

Nursing unit managers are the key clinical line managers who have direct responsibility and authority to deliver care, manage resources for their area of practice and educate staff within that specific context. This research analyzed the nurses' perception of how well done are such nursing roles. While not surprising, that study found a number of barriers to nurses being able to use the skills they have.

The present study demonstrates the socio-demographic characteristics. According to age (Mean= 38.7, and S.D =7.2), the higher percentage was in the age groups between (27- 37 years) which constituted (57.3 %), and the lower percentage of age groups (48-56 years) which constituted (9.1%). This finding is similar to finding of [6]. In their findings out of the (220) subjects involved in this study, their age ranged from (20-29) years of age and comprised (58.6%) of the study sample. That the most of nurses were (50.9 %) from females. This result is an agreement with study of [7] Which they mentioned in their study Factors affecting job satisfaction among nurses working in Ondo state that the (86.7%) of the total respondents are female, confirming that the female gender dominates the nursing profession. The education level of nurses the higher percentage was (54.5%) who were graduate from nursing diploma, while the lower percentages (18.2 %) who were graduate from nursing college. This result is a similar study conducted by [8]), Which they explained in their study Factors Affecting Performance of Professional Nurses in A Tertiary Care Hospital, Rawalpindi that the majority of subjects (63%) had Diploma in general nursing & midwifery.

Finally, most of the nurses have services years between (2-12 years) which was (65.5%), while (10 %) have services years from 23 years and above. This result varies with outcome with the study of [9] that showed that (40.6%) had worked for 21 years or above.

Factors Affecting of Nursing Work Performance

The results of the study showed that Challenges of the nursing field and the intense workload factors come in first rank, the best mechanism for the motivations underlying people's resilience and drive for success is still self-support. Strive to fulfill their ideals, as this will have a significant effect on boosting the motivation system and identifying what can provide the worker a sense of loyalty and honesty when completing tasks. This finding is agreement with [10] who looked into what factors influence employee turnover and evaluated how satisfied people are with the current incentive management system and how much it inspires staff. additionally, he offered suggestions for enhancing the Incentive Management System. A convenience sample of all medical professionals employed by Sudi Arabia, Riyadh's Department of Pathology and Laboratory Medicine (DPLM) was used by the researchers. The sample size was 250. The majority of respondents—51 percent—strongly agreed that the primary cause of employee turnover during the COVID-19 epidemic was disparities in wage distribution or inadequate salaries. 48% strongly concurred that it was low.

The data analysis shows that there are no significant statistical factors affecting nurses' performance and their age, gender, and services years. Also, indicates that there is a significant relationship between the factors affecting nurses' and their level of education. This result is a similar to finding of [3], They found the same result in their study on Factors Affecting of Nursing Work Performance at Al- Hamdaniya General Hospital in Mosul City.

Conclusion

This study revealed a low level of salary and career development among nurses. Implementing management scheduling with all administrative functions (planning, organizing, staffing, operation and

control) involves a great relationship with the level of nurses' performance, as the organizational and control aspect of nurses' scheduling is the main factor affecting the nurse's job performance.

References

- [1] Suweko H, Dwiantoro L. Kepemimpinan transformasional dalam meningkatkan kepuasan kerja perawat: literature review. *J Ilm Keperawatan Kebidanan*. 2020;11(1):106–112.
- [2] Rizany I, Hariyati RTS, Afifah E, Rusdiyansyah. The impact of nurse scheduling management on nurses' job satisfaction in Army Hospital: cross-sectional research. *Sage Open*. 2019;9(2):2158244019856189. doi:10.1177/2158244019856189
- [3] Mukhlif HH, Saeed Al. Factors affecting of nursing work performance at Al-Hamdaniya General Hospital in Mosul City. *Kufa J Nurs Sci*. 2021;11(2):71–78.
- [4] Hamid AYS, Hariyati RTS. Improving nurses' performance through remuneration: a literature review. *Enfermería Clínica*. 2018;28:130–133.
- [5] Sari DP, Saputera B, Saleh M, Sholihah Q, Daud I. Factors affecting nurse performance in medical ward. *J Nurs Health Sci*. 2020;9(4).
- [6] Hussein ZA, Saadon NY. Assessment of nurses challenges regarding health care system in Hilla City. *Ann RSCB*. 2021;25(6):530–539.
- [7] Olaniyan JO, Adetunji KM, Adetunji AA. Factors affecting job satisfaction among nurses working in Ondo state. *Future Bus J*. 2023;9(1):87.
- [8] Yasir S, Majeed S, Khan A. Factors affecting performance of professional nurses in a tertiary care hospital, Rawalpindi. *Int J Sci Res Publ*. 2022;12(2):622. doi:10.29322/ijsrp.12.2.2022.p12276
- [9] Adatara P, Kuug A, Nyande F, Opare FY, Apaaye MA, Achaliwie F, Dotse W. A cross-sectional study to examine perspective of nursing unit managers on factors affecting the effective performance of their roles in the Volta Regional Hospital, Ghana. *Pyrex J Nurs Midwifery*. 2016;2(1):1–6.
- [10] Al-Qathmi A, Zedan H. The effect of incentive management system on turnover rate, job satisfaction and motivation of medical laboratory technologists. *Health Serv Res Manag Epidemiol*. 2021;8:233339282098840. doi:10.1177/2333392820988404

